

$$T_{21} = t^2 - \sigma_1^2 = t^2 - S_2 = t^2 - \frac{1}{4};$$

$$T_{31} = t^3 - \sigma_1^2 t = t^3 - S_2 t = t^3 - \frac{1}{2}t;$$

$$T_{41} = t^4 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^2 + \sigma_2^2 = t^4 - S_2 t^2 + \left(\frac{S_1^2}{2} - \frac{S_2}{2}\right)^2 = t^4 - \frac{3}{4}t^2 + \frac{1}{16};$$

$$T_{51} = t^5 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^3 + \sigma_2^2 t = t^5 - S_2 t^3 + \left(\frac{S_1^2}{2} - \frac{S_2}{2}\right)^2 t = t^5 - t^3 + \frac{3}{16}t;$$

$$T_{61} = t^6 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^4 + (\sigma_2^2 - 2\sigma_1\sigma_3)t^2 - \sigma_3^2 = t^6 - S_2 t^4 + \frac{1}{2}(S_2^2 - S_4)t^2 - \sigma_3^2 = \\ = t^6 - \frac{5}{4}t^4 + \frac{3}{8}t^2 - \frac{1}{64};$$

$$T_{71} = t^7 - (\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)t^5 + (\sigma_2^2 - 2\sigma_1\sigma_3)t^3 - \sigma_3^2 t = t^7 - S_2 t^5 + \frac{1}{2}(S_2^2 - S_4)t^3 - \sigma_3^2 t = \\ = t^7 - \frac{3}{2}t^5 + \frac{5}{8}t^3 - \frac{1}{16}t.$$

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MAXIMISATION OF CONDITIONAL MUTUAL INFORMATION

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Abstract

In this paper we consider mutual information for a pair of random variables and find a third variable (condition) that maximise conditional mutual information of three of them.

Keywords: Mutual information, conditional mutual information, entropy, information inequality, Lagrange theorem, conditional extremum.

1 Solution

Let A , B and X take two values for convenience. We will solve the problem using methods from the optimal control course. In entropy, we take the natural logarithm for ease of differentiation. Consider $I(A;B|X)$ as a function of p_{ijk} :

$$I(A; B|X) = H(A, X) + H(B, X) - H(A, B, X) - H(X) = \\ = \sum_{i,k} p_{ik} \log(p_{ik}) = \sum_{i,k} \left(\sum_j p_{ijk} \right) \log \left(\sum_j p_{ijk} \right) \log(p_k) =$$

Here the values A have the index i , the values B have the index j , the values X have the index k . Now let's express everything in terms of p_{ijk} :

Similarly with $H(B,X)$ and $H(X)$. Let us now differentiate the expression with respect to all p_{ijk} :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_{ijk}} [I(A; B|X)] &= \\ &= -[\log(p_{ik}) + \log(p_{jk}) - \log(p_{ijk}) - \log(p_k)] \end{aligned}$$

We are faced with the task of finding a conditional extremum for the function $I(A,B|X)$ with constraints

$$\begin{cases} p_{111} + p_{112} = p_{11}^{AB} \\ p_{121} + p_{122} = p_{12}^{AB} \\ p_{211} + p_{212} = p_{21}^{AB} \\ p_{221} + p_{222} = p_{22}^{AB} \end{cases}$$

and condition $p_{ijk} \geq 0$. We introduce the following functions:

$$\begin{cases} f_1 = p_{111} + p_{112} - p_{11}^{AB} \\ f_2 = p_{121} + p_{122} - p_{12}^{AB} \\ f_3 = p_{211} + p_{212} - p_{21}^{AB} \\ f_4 = p_{221} + p_{222} - p_{22}^{AB} \end{cases}$$

and construct the Lagrange function

$$F = I(A, B|X) + \lambda_1 f_1 + \lambda_2 f_2 + \lambda_3 f_3 + \lambda_4 f_4$$

Then we get the system of equations

$$\begin{cases} F'_{p_{111}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{112}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{121}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{122}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{211}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{212}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{221}} = 0 \\ F'_{p_{222}} = 0 \\ f_1 = 0 \\ f_2 = 0 \\ f_3 = 0 \\ f_4 = 0 \end{cases}$$

which gives for $k = 1, 2$ a system of 12 equations

$$\begin{cases} -[\log(p_{1*1k}) + \log(p_{*1k}) - \log(p_{11k}) - \log(p_{**k})] + \lambda_1 = 0 \\ -[\log(p_{1*2k}) + \log(p_{*2k}) - \log(p_{12k}) - \log(p_{**k})] + \lambda_2 = 0 \\ -[\log(p_{2*1k}) + \log(p_{*1k}) - \log(p_{21k}) - \log(p_{**k})] + \lambda_3 = 0 \\ -[\log(p_{2*2k}) + \log(p_{*2k}) - \log(p_{22k}) - \log(p_{**k})] + \lambda_4 = 0 \\ p_{111} + p_{112} = p_{11}^{AB} \\ p_{121} + p_{122} = p_{12}^{AB} \\ p_{211} + p_{212} = p_{21}^{AB} \\ p_{221} + p_{222} = p_{22}^{AB} \end{cases}$$

which is reduced to the form

$$\begin{cases} p_{1*1}p_{*11} = e^{\lambda_1} p_{111}p_{**1} \\ p_{1*2}p_{*12} = e^{\lambda_1} p_{112}p_{**2} \\ p_{1*1}p_{*21} = e^{\lambda_2} p_{121}p_{**1} \\ p_{1*2}p_{*22} = e^{\lambda_2} p_{122}p_{**2} \\ p_{2*1}p_{*11} = e^{\lambda_3} p_{211}p_{**1} \\ p_{2*2}p_{*12} = e^{\lambda_3} p_{212}p_{**2} \\ p_{2*1}p_{*21} = e^{\lambda_4} p_{221}p_{**1} \\ p_{2*2}p_{*22} = e^{\lambda_4} p_{222}p_{**2} \\ p_{111} + p_{112} = p_{11}^{AB} \\ p_{121} + p_{122} = p_{12}^{AB} \\ p_{211} + p_{212} = p_{21}^{AB} \\ p_{221} + p_{222} = p_{22}^{AB} \end{cases}$$

Let's solve the distribution system from last year's exchange rate

$$AB = \begin{pmatrix} 0.2 & 0.2 \\ 0.0 & 0.6 \end{pmatrix}$$

Knowing that p_{211} and p_{212} are equal to zero, we simplify the system to

$$\begin{cases} p_{111} + p_{121} = e^{\lambda_1}(p_{111} + p_{121} + p_{221}) \\ 0.4 - p_{111} - p_{121} = e^{\lambda_1}(1 - p_{111} - p_{121} - p_{221}) \\ (p_{111} + p_{121})(p_{121} + p_{221}) = e^{\lambda_2} p_{121}(p_{111} + p_{121} + p_{221}) \\ (0.4 - p_{111} - p_{121})(0.8 - p_{121} - p_{221}) = e^{\lambda_2} p_{122}(1 - p_{111} - p_{121} - p_{221}) \\ p_{121} + p_{221} = e^{\lambda_4}(p_{111} + p_{121} + p_{221}) \\ 0.8 - p_{121} - p_{221} = e^{\lambda_4}(1 - p_{111} - p_{121} - p_{221}) \end{cases}$$

We will solve the system by dividing rows with the same factors. We get equations of the following form:

$$\frac{p_{*11}}{p_{*21}} = e^{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \frac{p_{111}}{p_{121}}$$

Knowing that p_{211} and p_{212} are equal to zero, we get

$$\begin{aligned} p_{*11} &= p_{111} + p_{211} = p_{111} \\ p_{*12} &= p_{112} + p_{212} = p_{112} \end{aligned}$$

So our equations give us

$$\begin{aligned} p_{121} &= e^{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}(p_{121} + p_{221}) \\ p_{122} &= e^{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}(p_{122} + p_{222}) \end{aligned}$$

Adding the resulting expressions, we have

$$p_{12}^{AB} = e^{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}(p_{12}^{AB} + p_{22}^{AB})$$

substituting $p_{12}^{AB} = 0.2$, $p_{22}^{AB} = 0.6$, we get $e^{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} = 4$. Due to this, the equations obtained above turn into

$$\frac{p_{*11}}{p_{*21}} = 4 \cdot \frac{p_{111}}{p_{121}}$$

which, by expressing the left-hand side in terms of p_{ijk} , are reduced to the form

$$p_{121}p_{211} = 4 \cdot p_{111}p_{221}$$

Since $p_{211}^{AB} = 0$ and the probabilities are non-negative, in our example p_{211} and p_{212} are equal to zero. Thus, on the right side, either p_{111} or p_{221} must be zero. Let $p_{121} = 0$. Then $p_{122} = p_{12}^{AB} = 0.2$. Thus, sets of solutions are obtained by choosing a zero term in each pair of probabilities. But not all $2^3 = 8$ sets suit us. Indeed, let us turn to the first two equations of the simplified system. In fact we have

Dividing these equations by each other to eliminate a_1 , we get

$$\begin{cases} x = a_1 y \\ 0.4 - x = a_1(1 - y) \end{cases}$$

$$x = 4y$$

In this way,

$$p_{221} = 3/2(p_{111} + p_{121})$$

Because of this, we only have 2 sets of solutions

$$\begin{cases} p_{111} = 0.2 \\ p_{112} = 0.0 \\ p_{121} = 0.2 \\ p_{122} = 0.0 \\ p_{211} = 0.0 \\ p_{212} = 0.0 \\ p_{221} = 0.6 \\ p_{222} = 0.0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} p_{111} = 0.0 \\ p_{112} = 0.0 \\ p_{121} = 0.2 \\ p_{122} = 0.2 \\ p_{211} = 0.0 \\ p_{212} = 0.0 \\ p_{221} = 0.0 \\ p_{222} = 0.6 \end{cases}$$

Both solutions, as can be seen, satisfy the simplified system. It is necessary to find the maximum among them. Let us prove that the maximum is the first option, and the remaining points are not. To do this, we calculate the angular minors of orders $2m + 1, \dots, m + n$ (where m is the number of bonds, n is the number of variables) of the matrix

$$L = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \text{m столбцов} \\ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{array} \right) \end{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \text{n столбцов} \\ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_n} \end{array} \right) \end{matrix} \\ \left. \begin{matrix} \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_1} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_2} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_2} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_3} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial x_n} & \frac{\partial \varphi_2}{\partial x_n} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial x_n} \end{matrix} \right\} \begin{matrix} \text{m строк} \\ \left(\begin{array}{cccc} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_1 \partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_1 \partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_2 \partial x_1} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_2^2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_2 \partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_2 \partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_3 \partial x_1} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_3 \partial x_2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_3^2} & \dots & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_3 \partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_n \partial x_1} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_n \partial x_2} & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_n \partial x_3} & \dots & \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x_n^2} \end{array} \right) \end{matrix} \end{matrix}$$

The derivatives of the bonds are either 1 or 0, so, for example, the matrix in the upper right corner looks like this:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1.0 & 1.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 1.0 & 1.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 1.0 & 1.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 1.0 & 1.0 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the matrix in the lower left corner is obtained by transposing it. Now it remains to find the Hessian of the function F :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1^2} & \dots & \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_1 \partial x_n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_n \partial x_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_n^2} \end{pmatrix}$$

The second derivatives of the F function look like this:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_{111}^2} = \frac{1}{p_{111}} + \frac{1}{p_{111} + p_{121} + p_{211} + p_{221}} - \frac{1}{p_{111} + p_{121}} - \frac{1}{p_{111} + p_{211}}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_{121} \partial p_{111}} = \frac{1}{p_{111} + p_{121} + p_{211} + p_{221}} - \frac{1}{p_{111} + p_{121}}$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_{122} \partial p_{111}} = 0$$

Substituting the values of the obtained distributions into these formulas, we obtain for the first variant that For other options, this is not the case. **Theorem.** Let there be a function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$:

$\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and m constraint equations

$$H_{2m+1} = H_9 < 0$$

$$H_{2m+2} = H_{10} > 0$$

$$H_{2m+3} = H_{11} < 0$$

$$H_{2m+4} = H_{m+n} = H_{12} > 0$$

$$\varphi_1(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \dots = \varphi_m(x_1, \dots, x_n) = 0$$

where $m < n$. The Lagrange function for this problem is the function

$$F(x_1, \dots, x_n, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m) = f + \lambda_1 \varphi_1 + \dots + \lambda_m \varphi_m$$

Then the necessary conditions for the presence of a conditional extremum are given by the system of equations

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial F}{\partial x_i} = 0; (i = \overline{1, n}) \\ \varphi_j = 0; (j = \overline{1, m}) \end{cases}$$

Theorem. Let $M(x_1^0, \dots, x_n^0)$ be the critical point for the conditional extremum of the function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$. Then

1. If the signs of the angular minors $H_{2m+1}, \dots, H_{m+n}$ of the matrix L coincide with the sign of $(-1)^m$, then the stationary point under study is a conditional minimum point of the function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$;

2. If the signs of the angular minors $H_{2m+1}, \dots, H_{m+n}$ of the matrix L alternate, and the sign of the minor H_{2m+1} coincides with the sign of $(-1)^{m+1}$, then the stationary point under study is the conditional maximum point of the function $f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$.

Definition. Let $G \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be the set on which the functions $\varphi_i(x)$ are defined. Let $E = \{x \in G : \varphi_i(x) = 0 \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$. Let a function $f(x)$ be defined on G . The point $x_0 \in E$ is called the conditional extremum point of the given function with respect to the constraint equations if it is the point of the unconditional (absolute) extremum of the function f on the set E .

Conclusion. Since the conditions of the connection functions f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4 are nonexcludable due to the fact that we are dealing with probabilities, the found point is the absolute maximum point of the function $I(A; B|X)$.
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